

RAMP: A Protocol for Human Oversight of Autonomous Agents

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ABSTRACT

Autonomous AI agents are rapidly transitioning from research prototypes to production systems that take consequential actions on behalf of human principals: spending money, sending communications, and modifying infrastructure. The agent protocol ecosystem has standardized tool access (Model Context Protocol, MCP) and inter-agent coordination (Agent-to-Agent Protocol, A2A). However, the Agent-to-Human supervisory channel lacks an open protocol integrating mandatory temporal safety bounds, declarative multi-tenant governance, and cryptographic auditability.

We present **RAMP** (Remote Agent Monitoring Protocol), a transport-agnostic, cryptographically verifiable protocol that fills this gap. RAMP defines five primitives (telemetry, notifications, action requests, governance policies, and audit trail) organized into three functions: **Observe** (what is the agent doing?), **Decide** (should the agent do this?), and **Govern** (what is the agent allowed to do?). The protocol specifies a state-machine agent lifecycle, HMAC-SHA256 message integrity with replay protection, a declarative governance engine with six normative rule types and formal precedence ordering, and a tamper-evident hash-chained audit trail.

We provide a formal specification, a reference gateway and Python SDK achieving Level 3 conformance (full governance and audit), and a positioning analysis demonstrating RAMP as complementary to MCP and A2A. The specification, implementation, and SDK are open-source under the Apache 2.0 license.¹

KEYWORDS

autonomous agents, human-in-the-loop, agent governance, protocol design, human oversight, AI safety, agent-to-human communication

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Rise of Consequential Agents

Autonomous AI agents, software systems that perceive, reason, and act with minimal human intervention, are transitioning from experimental prototypes into production systems that operate continuously on behalf of human principals. The emergence of large language models as the reasoning core of these agents has accelerated this transition: agent orchestration frameworks such as LangChain [5], LangGraph [15], CrewAI [19], AutoGen [36], and OpenAI’s Agents SDK [22] have lowered the barrier to building multi-step, tool-using agents. Open-source platforms such as OpenClaw [23] and enterprise offerings including Salesforce Agentforce and Microsoft Copilot Studio now provide agent-as-a-service deployment. Concurrently, regulatory frameworks are imposing explicit requirements on human oversight of AI systems: the European

Union’s AI Act mandates “effective human oversight” for high-risk AI systems (Article 14) [8], and ISO/IEC 42001 requires auditable records of AI system decisions [14].

A qualitative shift is underway: agents now take *consequential actions* on behalf of human principals, from booking flights and executing financial transactions to sending communications and modifying production infrastructure.² Unlike traditional software that executes deterministic instructions, these agents make autonomous decisions with real-world consequences. This raises a fundamental question: *how should agents communicate with the humans they serve?*

1.2 The Protocol Gap

The agent communication ecosystem has partially matured through two complementary protocol efforts:

- **Model Context Protocol (MCP)** [3], developed by Anthropic, standardizes Agent-to-Tool communication. MCP defines how agents discover, access, and invoke tools and data sources through a Host/Client/Server architecture.
- **Agent-to-Agent Protocol (A2A)** [11], developed by Google, standardizes Agent-to-Agent communication. A2A defines how agents discover, delegate to, and coordinate with one another through Agent Cards and a Task lifecycle.

Neither protocol addresses the *Agent-to-Human* supervisory channel. MCP provides a client-side tool approval mechanism within its sampling flow, but this is a binary allow/deny gate with no risk metadata, no timeout semantics, no governance enforcement, and no audit trail. A2A defines a Task lifecycle with an “input needed” state, but has no concept of human principal, governance policy, or tamper-evident audit.

The result is that every agent framework independently invents its own human interaction mechanism: coding agents dump output to terminals, scheduling agents send Slack messages, financial agents send emails. These ad-hoc approaches share common deficits:

- (1) **No mandatory safety guarantees.** Agents hang indefinitely awaiting human input, with no timeout or fallback behavior.
- (2) **No structured risk communication.** Humans receive approve/deny prompts with no information about reversibility, cost, or impact.
- (3) **No cross-agent governance.** There is no standard way to impose spending limits, capability constraints, or operating-hours restrictions across heterogeneous agent deployments.
- (4) **No auditable record.** There is no tamper-evident log of what an agent requested and which human approved it.

¹<https://github.com/fahaddeshmukh/RAMP>

²In 2024, Air Canada was held liable after its customer-service chatbot autonomously promised a bereavement fare discount that did not exist, illustrating the legal risk of unsupervised agent actions [6].

These deficits compound at scale: an organization deploying dozens of heterogeneous agents lacks a unified mechanism to monitor their collective state, impose cross-agent spending limits, or maintain a single audit trail spanning all agent actions.

1.3 Regulatory Motivation

Beyond practical engineering needs, regulatory frameworks are creating legal requirements for human oversight of AI systems. Article 14 of the EU AI Act [8] requires that high-risk AI systems be designed such that natural persons can “understand the relevant capacities and limitations of the AI system,” “correctly interpret the high-risk AI system’s output,” and “decide, in any particular situation, not to use the high-risk AI system or to otherwise disregard, override or reverse the output.” ISO/IEC 42001 [14] specifies controls for logging and auditing AI system decisions.

These frameworks define *what* must be done (oversight, auditability, governability) but not *how* at the protocol level. No existing open standard, as of this writing, provides the wire-level primitives needed to satisfy these requirements across heterogeneous agent deployments.

1.4 Contributions

This paper presents RAMP (Remote Agent Monitoring Protocol), an open protocol for Agent-to-Human communication. Our contributions are:

- (1) **Protocol design.** We define a transport-agnostic protocol for Agent-to-Human communication with five primitives: telemetry, notifications, action requests (human-in-the-loop), governance policies, and audit trail. The protocol features a seven-state agent lifecycle, HMAC-SHA256 message integrity based on RFC 8785-compatible canonical JSON [26], and mandatory timeout-with-fallback semantics on all human-in-the-loop interactions.
- (2) **Governance engine.** We introduce a declarative, gateway-enforced governance engine as a core protocol primitive, not an extension or product feature. The engine defines six normative rule types (mandatory human approval, capability scope, resource constraints, time constraints, rate limits, and aggregate cross-agent budgets) plus conditional auto-resolution, with a formally specified precedence ordering. To our knowledge, this is the first open protocol to embed declarative governance, including cross-agent budget enforcement, capability scoping, and temporal safety bounds, at the agent-to-human communication layer.
- (3) **Reference implementation.** We demonstrate the protocol’s implementability through a reference gateway (FastAPI, Python) and SDK (Python) that together achieve Level 3 conformance (full governance and audit), validated by a comprehensive test suite covering policy enforcement, cryptographic verification, state machine validation, and audit trail integrity.
- (4) **Positioning analysis.** We show that RAMP is complementary to MCP (Agent-to-Tool) and A2A (Agent-to-Agent), completing what we term the *agent protocol triangle*: the minimal protocol surface required for safe, auditable, governance-compliant deployment.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 surveys related work in agent protocols, human-in-the-loop systems, and AI governance. Section 3 presents the RAMP protocol design. Section 4 describes the reference implementation. Section 5 demonstrates a complete interaction. Section 6 analyzes design tradeoffs, security properties, and limitations. Section 7 outlines future work, and Section 8 concludes.

2 BACKGROUND & RELATED WORK

2.1 Agent Communication Protocols

2.1.1 Model Context Protocol (MCP). MCP [3] defines a client-server architecture for agent-tool interaction. An MCP Host (the application) manages one or more MCP Clients, each connected to an MCP Server that exposes Resources (data), Tools (executable functions), and Prompts (templates). MCP supports two transports: stdio for local processes and HTTP with Server-Sent Events for remote servers.

MCP includes a *sampling* capability in which an MCP server can request the host’s language model to generate a completion. The specification notes that “the human should always be in the loop for approving sampling requests” [3]. This mechanism provides a client-side human gate, but it is architecturally distinct from what RAMP provides: it is binary (allow/deny), carries no structured risk metadata, has no timeout or fallback semantics, imposes no governance constraints, and produces no audit trail. The approval decision exists only in the host application’s memory.

2.1.2 Agent-to-Agent Protocol (A2A). A2A [11] defines a protocol for inter-agent communication. Agents publish Agent Cards describing their capabilities, and communicate through a Task lifecycle with states including submitted, working, input-required, completed, and failed. A2A supports streaming via Server-Sent Events and defines an Artifact model for structured outputs.

A2A’s input-required state superficially resembles RAMP’s action requests, but it is designed for agent-to-agent information exchange, not human oversight. It carries no risk assessment, no timeout-with-fallback, no governance policy evaluation, and no tamper-evident audit record. A2A has no concept of a human principal, governance policy, or compliance audit.

2.1.3 Agent Protocol. The AI Engineer Foundation’s Agent Protocol [1] defines a minimal REST API for agent task management. It specifies task creation, status polling, and artifact retrieval. It does not address human-in-the-loop interaction, governance, or audit.

2.2 Human-in-the-Loop Systems

The concept of structured human-machine interaction has a rich history. Sheridan’s levels of automation [29] define a ten-level taxonomy ranging from full human control to full machine autonomy, with intermediate levels requiring human approval, consent, or veto. Parasuraman et al. [24] refine this into a four-stage model (information acquisition, information analysis, decision selection, action implementation), noting that automation at each stage has distinct implications for human performance.

In machine learning, human-in-the-loop (HITL) workflows are well-established for data labeling and active learning [18, 28]. However, these systems are data-centric: the human labels training examples, not authorizes real-world actions. They operate within closed pipelines, not as protocol-level interoperability layers.

Enterprise approval workflows (ServiceNow, Jira, Slack interactive messages) provide product-specific human gates, but each is a closed system with proprietary semantics. There is no interoperable protocol that enables agents from different frameworks to request human decisions through a common mechanism. The closest industry practice is *ChatOps*, using chat platforms such as Slack or Microsoft Teams for deployment approvals and operational decisions [34]. *ChatOps* relies on unstructured text matching, provides no formal risk metadata, and offers no cryptographic non-repudiation or tamper-evident audit trail. RAMP replaces this ad-hoc pattern with a structured, protocol-level mechanism that carries typed risk assessments, enforces mandatory timeouts, and produces auditable records.

Amershi et al. [2] propose 18 guidelines for human-AI interaction, including making clear what the system can do (G1), supporting efficient correction (G10), and providing explanation (G15). Shneiderman [30] advocates for “human-centered AI” that maintains human control while leveraging automation. RAMP operationalizes these principles at the protocol level: telemetry satisfies visibility requirements, action requests with risk assessments support informed decision-making, and governance policies enforce organizational constraints.

2.3 AI Governance & Regulatory Frameworks

The EU AI Act [8] establishes a risk-based classification for AI systems. Article 14 mandates that high-risk AI systems be designed with “effective human oversight,” including the ability for natural persons to “fully understand the capacities and limitations of the high-risk AI system,” “correctly interpret the system’s output,” and “be able to decide not to use the high-risk AI system or to otherwise disregard, override or reverse the output of the high-risk AI system.”

ISO/IEC 42001:2023 [14] defines an AI management system standard requiring documentation, monitoring, and audit of AI system behavior. The NIST AI Risk Management Framework [20] defines Govern, Map, Measure, and Manage functions for AI risk governance. IEEE P2863 [13] provides recommended practices for organizational governance of AI.

These frameworks specify governance *objectives* but not protocol-level *mechanisms*. RAMP provides the structural primitives (structured telemetry, risk-assessed action requests with mandatory timeout, declarative policy enforcement, and hash-chained audit) that architecturally support compliance with these objectives.

2.4 Tamper-Evident Logging

RAMP’s audit trail employs hash chaining, a technique with established provenance. Crosby and Wallach [7] formalize tamper-evident logging using hash-based data structures. Certificate Transparency [16] applies similar principles to TLS certificate issuance, creating publicly verifiable append-only logs. RAMP adapts this approach to agent governance: each audit record includes a SHA-256

hash of its contents and the hash of the preceding record, enabling sequential verification by any party with read access.

2.5 Concurrent Agent-to-Human Work

Concurrent with our work, two Agent-to-Human specifications emerged in February 2026, confirming A2H as an emerging protocol category. Liang et al. [17] define an A2H Protocol centered on human discoverability via a “Human Card” registry and four interaction primitives (Permission, Clarification, Solicitation, Notification). Twilio Labs [32] released an open-source A2H framework with five intent types (INFORM, COLLECT, AUTHORIZE, ESCALATE, RESULT) routed through a channel-agnostic gateway with JWS-signed consent evidence. These efforts validate the need for structured Agent-to-Human communication and inform RAMP’s design. Where Liang and Twilio focus on message delivery and human discoverability, RAMP builds on this foundation by embedding governance, mandatory temporal safety bounds, and cryptographic auditability as first-class protocol primitives.

2.6 Gateway-Level Governance

The concept of placing governance at a communication proxy is well-established in cloud-native infrastructure. AgentGateway [31], donated to the Linux Foundation by Solo.io, provides infrastructure-level policy enforcement for A2A and MCP traffic. The MI9 framework [33] offers FSM-based runtime behavioral monitoring with graduated containment strategies for agentic AI. Infrastructure-level policy engines such as Open Policy Agent [21] evaluate arbitrary policies over arbitrary inputs. These systems operate at the agent-to-tool or agent-to-system layer; none defines a wire protocol for structured human arbitration with timeout guarantees, typed risk assessments, or cross-agent budget constraints. RAMP operates at a distinct architectural layer, the agent-to-human communication channel, and embeds domain-specific governance as a protocol primitive rather than deferring to external policy engines.

2.7 Risk Assessment Frameworks

The AURA framework [27] introduces gamma-based risk scoring for autonomous agent assessment. RAMP’s mandatory risk assessment on Action Requests (section 3) provides complementary capabilities: AURA scores can feed into RAMP’s Corroboration Hook for independent risk verification at the gateway layer.

3 RAMP PROTOCOL DESIGN

3.1 Design Principles

RAMP is governed by five design principles, each motivated by observed failures in existing agent oversight approaches:

- (1) **Transport-agnostic.** RAMP defines message semantics, not wire format. Conformant implementations may use HTTP, WebSocket, gRPC, or MQTT. This follows the principle that protocol longevity depends on decoupling semantics from transport [10].
- (2) **Minimal agent burden.** An agent must be able to emit a valid RAMP message with a single HTTP POST using only a standard library. This reduces the adoption barrier, consistent with Postel’s robustness principle [4]: “be liberal in what you accept, conservative in what you send.” In practice, this means that

the protocol’s mechanical requirements (cryptographic signing, state tracking, sequence numbering, and envelope construction) are absorbed by deterministic host-side code (an SDK or tool wrapper), not by the agent’s reasoning process. For LLM-based agents, this separation is particularly important: the agent’s prompt need only contain a semantic tool description (e.g., “call `request_approval` with a justification and risk level”), while all protocol mechanics execute outside the inference path. This ensures that RAMP compliance does not compete with the agent’s primary task for representational capacity.

- (3) **Safe by default.** All human-in-the-loop requests must include a timeout and fallback action. An agent must never hang indefinitely awaiting human input. This mandatory safety guarantee is, to our knowledge, absent from all existing agent HITL mechanisms, including MCP’s sampling approval and A2A’s input-required state.
- (4) **Auditable by design.** Every state transition and human decision produces an immutable, hash-chained audit record. This is not an optional extension but a core protocol requirement at Level 3 conformance.
- (5) **Governance-first.** The protocol natively supports declarative policy enforcement as a core primitive. This reflects the position that governance must be embedded in the communication layer, not bolted on as a product feature. Existing protocols (MCP, A2A) have no governance story; the absence of governance at the protocol layer forces every deployment to reinvent it.

3.2 Architectural Roles

RAMP defines three architectural roles (Figure 1):

- **Human Principal.** The person with authority over one or more agents. Sets governance policies, approves consequential actions, and receives notifications. Principals interact through client applications (mobile, web, CLI) that connect to the Gateway.
- **Agent.** The autonomous AI system performing tasks on behalf of the Principal. Reports telemetry, sends notifications, and requests human approval before taking high-risk actions.
- **Gateway.** The server-side intermediary that receives messages from agents, enforces governance policies, routes messages to principals, and maintains the audit trail. All RAMP messages pass through the Gateway.

The gateway-mediated architecture is a deliberate design choice. A direct agent-to-human channel would preclude server-side policy enforcement, centralized audit, multi-agent budget aggregation, and principal availability decoupling (the principal need not be online when the agent sends a message; the Gateway queues and delivers when the principal connects). The tradeoff is an additional network hop, which adds latency on the order of milliseconds, negligible relative to the seconds-to-minutes timescale of human decision-making.

This three-role model is structurally analogous to OAuth 2.0’s Resource Owner / Client / Authorization Server separation [12], where a trusted intermediary enforces access policy between the entity requesting access and the entity granting it.

Figure 1. The three agent communication channels. MCP standardizes Agent-to-Tool access; A2A standardizes Agent-to-Agent coordination. RAMP fills the missing Agent-to-Human supervisory channel via a governance Gateway.

Figure 2. RAMP agent lifecycle state machine. Seven states with explicit valid transitions. Solid arrows show forward transitions; dashed arrows show recovery paths; dotted arrows converge on the absorbing terminal state. SUSPENDED is reachable from any active state via human or policy action.

3.3 Agent Lifecycle State Machine

Every RAMP-conformant agent models its execution as a finite state machine with seven states (Figure 2):

- **REGISTERED:** Agent has authenticated but has not started executing.
- **IDLE:** Running but not actively performing a task.
- **EXECUTING:** Actively working on a task.
- **AWAITING_HUMAN_INPUT:** Paused, waiting for a human decision.
- **SUSPENDED:** Paused by a human principal or policy enforcement.
- **ERRORED:** Encountered a non-fatal error; may recover.
- **TERMINATED:** Stopped. Terminal state.

The Gateway enforces valid transitions: a message declaring an invalid state transition (e.g., `IDLE` → `AWAITING_HUMAN_INPUT` without an Action Request) is rejected. Key invariants include: (1) an agent sending an Action Request must transition to `AWAITING_HUMAN_INPUT`; (2) a principal may force any non-terminal agent to `SUSPENDED` at any time (the “kill switch”); (3) `TERMINATED` is absorbing; no transitions out.

3.4 Message Primitives

RAMP messages share a common envelope containing protocol version, UUID v7 message identifier (chosen over UUID v4 for its embedded timestamp component, which enables chronological ordering of messages without requiring clock synchronization between agent and gateway), message type, session identifier, agent and principal identifiers, monotonic sequence number, timestamp, cryptographic nonce, HMAC-SHA256 signature, and a type-specific payload. The five primitive types are organized into three functional groups:

3.4.1 Observe—What is the agent doing?

Telemetry. One-way messages (Agent → Gateway → Principal) reporting the agent’s current lifecycle state, task progress, and resource consumption (token usage, API calls, monetary cost). Agents should emit telemetry at least every 60 seconds during EXECUTING and every 300 seconds during IDLE. The Gateway uses telemetry data for resource constraint evaluation and unresponsiveness detection. Telemetry and notifications are deliberately one-way: the agent reports, the gateway relays and evaluates, and the principal observes. No acknowledgment is required, ensuring that telemetry emission never blocks agent execution.

Notifications. One-way informational messages carrying a priority level (low, normal, high, critical), category (completion, warning, error, info, cost_alert, security), and a body in plain-text or Markdown. Notifications do not require a human decision; they provide awareness.

3.4.2 Decide—Should the agent do this?

Action Requests. The core human-in-the-loop mechanism. An Action Request pauses agent execution and presents the human principal with structured options, a mandatory risk assessment, and a timeout with a safe fallback.

Each Action Request contains:

- **Options:** An ordered list of actions the human may choose from (not limited to approve/deny).
- **Risk assessment** (required): `risk_level` (low/medium/high/critical), `reversibility` (reversible/partially_reversible/irreversible), `estimated_cost_usd`, `impact_scope`, `action_category`, and `justification`.
- **Timeout:** Maximum wait time (up to 86,400 seconds). Required.
- **Fallback action:** The option executed if the timeout expires. Must reference one of the declared options.

The mandatory timeout-with-fallback is a key design constraint: it guarantees that no agent can hang indefinitely awaiting human input. If the human is unavailable, the system degrades to a pre-declared safe state rather than blocking.

Action Responses. Returned from the principal (via the Gateway) to the agent. Each response contains the selected option, resolver identity, and resolution type (`human_decision`, `timeout_fallback`, `policy_auto_approved`, `policy_auto_denied`, `delegated`, `escalated`), and optional free-form input.

3.4.3 Govern—What is the agent allowed to do?

Governance Policies. Declarative, per-agent rule sets evaluated at the Gateway before message delivery. Six normative rule types are defined, each independently evaluated against incoming messages and Action Requests. Section 3.6 details the governance engine.

Audit Trail. Every meaningful event (state transitions, action requests, resolutions, policy violations, suspensions) produces a hash-chained audit record. Each record includes a SHA-256 hash of its contents and the hash of the preceding record, enabling sequential tamper-detection by any party with read access. Section 3.7 details the audit model.

3.5 Message Security

RAMP employs layered integrity protection:

- **HMAC-SHA256 signatures.** Every message is signed using a shared secret established during agent registration. The signature is computed over an RFC 8785-compatible canonical JSON serialization [26] of the message envelope with the signature field removed. Canonical JSON ensures deterministic serialization across implementations, solving the interoperability problem that affects many signature-dependent protocols.
- **Replay protection.** Three mechanisms operate in conjunction: (1) a monotonically increasing `sequence_number` per session (the Gateway rejects non-increasing values); (2) a cryptographic nonce on every message, with the Gateway rejecting previously-seen (`message_id`, `nonce`) pairs within a 5-minute window; (3) a `timestamp` field, with the Gateway rejecting messages deviating more than 5 minutes from server time. This bounds the nonce cache to a fixed, predictable size.
- **Transport encryption.** All transports must use TLS 1.3 or later. HMAC signatures provide payload integrity even if TLS is compromised.

3.6 Governance Engine

The governance engine is the most architecturally distinctive element of RAMP. It defines a declarative policy model in which governance constraints are specified as rules in a per-agent policy document, evaluated at the Gateway before messages reach the human principal. This design ensures governance enforcement even when agents are untrusted or buggy.

3.6.1 Rule Types. RAMP defines six governance rules required for Level 3 gateway conformance, plus an optional auto-resolution mechanism:

- (1) **mandatory_hitl:** Forces human approval for actions at or above a specified risk level, overriding any automatic resolution rules. This is the highest-priority rule.
- (2) **action_scope:** Controls *what categories* of actions an agent may take, regardless of cost. Defines allowed and denied action categories matched against the `action_category` field in the risk assessment. This prevents the scenario where a \$0-cost action (e.g., sending an email) bypasses all cost-based controls. This mechanism applies beyond financial actions to any capability category: email access, database operations, file system writes, or API invocations.
- (3) **resource_constraint:** Per-agent spending limits scoped to a session or time window.

Figure 3. Policy evaluation precedence. Rules are evaluated top-to-bottom; a deny at any normative level (1–6) short-circuits to the right. auto_resolution applies only if no higher-priority rule has triggered.

- (4) **time_constraint**: Restricts agent operation to specified days and hours (operating-hours enforcement).
- (5) **rate_constraint**: Limits message throughput to prevent spam and runaway loops.
- (6) **aggregate_constraint**: Controls total spending across *all* agents for a given principal. Prevents the exploit where N agents each spend just under the per-agent threshold, resulting in uncontrolled aggregate expenditure.

Auto-resolution (optional). The specification additionally defines `auto_resolution`, which enables automatic approval or denial of Action Requests when specified conditions are met (e.g., cost below a threshold). `auto_resolution` has the lowest precedence: it is always overridden by the six normative governance rules above. It is not required for Level 3 conformance.

Four informative (non-normative) extension types (`data_access`, `escalation`, `geo_constraint`, and `emergency_override`) are additionally specified for enterprise use cases.

3.6.2 Precedence Ordering. When multiple rules apply to the same Action Request, the Gateway evaluates them in a formally specified precedence order (Figure 3). The critical invariant is: a deny from rules 1–6 (normative) is *never* overridden by an `auto_resolution` rule. This prevents dangerous interactions such as an auto-approve rule permitting an action that should be blocked by capability scope.

3.6.3 Violation Responses. Each rule specifies an `on_violation` behavior: `deny_and_notify` (reject the action, notify the principal), `suspend_and_notify` (reject and suspend the agent), `suspend_all_and_notify` (suspend all agents for the principal, used by aggregate constraints), `suspend_until_allowed` (suspend but auto-resume when the constraint lifts, e.g., operating hours

reopen), and `throttle_and_warn` (drop excess messages, return rate-limit headers).

3.7 Audit Trail

The audit trail records 25 event types, including agent registration, state transitions, action requests, resolutions, policy violations, suspensions, resumptions, and emergency overrides. Each record includes:

- An event identifier, type, timestamp, and session/agent/principal identifiers.
- Event-specific details (e.g., which action was selected, which policy was violated).
- A full policy evaluation trace listing every rule evaluated and its result.
- An integrity block: SHA-256 hash of the record’s contents, hash of the preceding record, and the record’s position in the chain.

The Gateway stores records in append-only storage and supports a query API with filtering by agent, session, event type, principal, and time range. A dedicated verification endpoint enables any authorized party to validate chain integrity by recomputing hashes sequentially. An export endpoint supports JSON Lines and OpenTelemetry formats for integration with external SIEM systems.

3.8 Conformance Levels

RAMP defines four conformance levels, enabling incremental adoption:

- **Level 1 (Basic):** Telemetry, notifications, valid envelope with signature, lifecycle state modeling.
- **Level 2 (Interactive):** Level 1 plus Action Request/Response with timeout and fallback.
- **Level 3 (Governed):** Level 2 plus policy evaluation (the six normative rule types: `mandatory_hitl`, `action_scope`, `resource_constraint`, `time_constraint`, `rate_constraint`, `aggregate_constraint`), hash-chained audit, audit query API, state machine enforcement, and RFC 8785-compatible canonical JSON.
- **Level 4 (Enterprise, informative):** Level 3 plus multi-tenant routing, delegation, escalation, geo-constraints, and emergency override. This level is non-normative.

This graduated structure allows lightweight agents (e.g., a monitoring-only agent) to claim Level 1 conformance without implementing the full governance engine, while enterprise gateways can target Level 3 or Level 4. The approach is inspired by conformance profiles in specifications such as CSS [35] and HTTP content negotiation [9].

4 REFERENCE IMPLEMENTATION

To demonstrate implementability and validate the protocol design, we provide a reference implementation consisting of a gateway and an SDK.

4.1 Gateway

The reference gateway comprises three Python modules (`main.py`, `policies.py`, `store.py`)³ using FastAPI [25] for HTTP handling and aiosqlite for persistent audit storage. The gateway exposes an OpenAPI 3.1.0 specification for machine-readable API documentation and client code generation. It maintains agent state, session metadata, and policy documents in memory, with all audit records persisted to SQLite in append-only mode with hash chaining. The gateway implements Level 3 conformance, including the six Level 3-required governance rule types (`mandatory_hitl`, `action_scope`, `resource_constraint`, `time_constraint`, `rate_constraint`, `aggregate_constraint`), the full seven-state lifecycle with transition validation, HMAC-SHA256 signature verification, nonce and timestamp replay protection, and policy precedence evaluation.

4.2 SDK

The Python SDK comprises four modules (`agent.py`, `models.py`, `signing.py`, `__init__.py`) and provides an `async` with context manager that handles registration, session creation, telemetry, notifications, and action requests. It uses `httpx` for HTTP communication and implements HMAC-SHA256 signing with RFC 8785-compatible canonical JSON serialization. Action request resolution uses long-polling: the SDK repeatedly queries the gateway for a resolution, with configurable poll intervals and total timeout. From the agent developer’s perspective, the SDK reduces RAMP integration to four semantic calls (`send_telemetry`, `send_notification`, `request_action`, and session management via a context manager); all cryptographic, transport, and state-tracking logic is encapsulated. The repository additionally provides a self-contained CLI wrapper (`ramp_client.py`, 247 lines) packaged as a portable agent skill, enabling tool-use integration with any LLM-based agent framework without additional library dependencies.

4.3 Implementation Coverage

Table 1 summarizes the implementation status of specification features. All Level 3 normative features are fully implemented; the unimplemented features comprise optional mechanisms (auto-resolution, webhook verification, multi-party approval) and alternative transport bindings (WebSocket, MQTT). Features marked as not implemented (auto-resolution, webhook verification, multi-party approval, WebSocket and MQTT bindings) are fully specified and may be implemented by third parties or in future versions.

4.4 Test Suite

The implementation includes 42 tests (35 gateway, 7 SDK), achieving 97% statement coverage of the governance-critical policy engine (`policies.py`), 93% of the data model layer, and 100% of the cryptographic signing module:

- **Lifecycle:** Registration, session creation, state transitions, duplicate rejection.
- **HITL:** Full action request/response flow, long-poll resolution, timeout behavior.

³The gateway totals approximately 1,280 lines of Python; the SDK approximately 640 lines. Exact counts are verifiable in the repository.

Table 1. Implementation coverage of RAMP v0.2 specification features.

Feature	Impl.	Notes
State machine (7 states)	✓	Full transition validation
Telemetry + Notifications	✓	
Action Requests + Responses	✓	Including long-poll
HMAC-SHA256 + replay protection	✓	Nonce + timestamp + seq. no.
Hash-chained audit trail	✓	aiosqlite persistence
<code>mandatory_hitl</code>	✓	
<code>action_scope</code>	✓	Allow + deny lists
<code>resource_constraint</code>	✓	Session window
<code>time_constraint</code>	✓	Days + hours
<code>rate_constraint</code>	✓	Messages per window
<code>aggregate_constraint</code>	✓	Cross-agent budgets
<code>auto_resolution</code>	—	Specified, not impl.
Webhook verification	—	Specified, not impl.
Multi-party (N-of-M) approval	—	Specified, not impl.
WebSocket / MQTT bindings	—	HTTP binding only
Informative extensions	—	4 types specified

- **Governance:** Each of the six implemented rule types tested for both pass and violation, including aggregate constraint warning thresholds and cross-agent budget enforcement.
- **Security:** HMAC signature verification, wrong-key rejection, nonce replay detection, stale timestamp rejection, payload tampering detection, canonical JSON correctness.
- **Audit:** Hash chain integrity is validated implicitly through all gateway tests.

5 WALKTHROUGH: A COMPLETE HITL INTERACTION

We demonstrate the protocol through the included flight booking example (Figure 4). An agent searches for flights, finds options, and requests human approval to purchase a specific ticket.

- (1) **Registration.** The agent registers with the Gateway, declaring its identity, capabilities, and conformance level. The Gateway returns a shared secret for subsequent HMAC signing.
- (2) **Session creation.** The agent creates a session, establishing a monotonic sequence number namespace and audit scope.
- (3) **Telemetry.** The agent sends a telemetry message reporting EXECUTING state with task description “Searching flights...”
- (4) **Notification.** The agent sends a notification: “Found 3 flights: Delta, United, American.”
- (5) **Action Request.** The agent sends an Action Request:
 - Title: “Book Delta DL-402?”
 - Options: [Book Flight, Cancel]
 - Risk: high, irreversible, \$420
 - Timeout: 300 seconds; Fallback: Cancel

The agent transitions to AWAITING_HUMAN_INPUT.

- (6) **Policy evaluation.** The Gateway evaluates the agent’s policy document: `action_scope` permits “purchase”; `resource_constraint` confirms the cost is within the session budget; `time_constraint` confirms within operating hours. All rules pass.
- (7) **Policy denial (governance enforcement).** Earlier in the session, the agent attempted to send a promotional email on the principal’s behalf. The Gateway evaluated `action_scope` and found “email” absent from the agent’s allowed categories. The

Figure 4. Sequence diagram of a complete HITL interaction. The agent registers, reports progress via telemetry, requests human approval for a booking action, and proceeds after receiving the principal’s decision. The Gateway evaluates governance policies before delivering the request.

Gateway returned RAMP-4003 (action scope denied), created a `policy_violation` audit record, and the agent continued to the flight booking without interruption. This illustrates that the governance engine actively rejects out-of-scope actions, not only permits compliant ones.

- (8) **Delivery.** The Gateway delivers the Action Request to the human principal.
- (9) **Resolution.** The principal selects “Book Flight.” The Gateway creates an `action_resolved` audit record with the full policy evaluation trace, and delivers the Action Response to the agent.
- (10) **Execution.** The agent receives the response, transitions to EXECUTING, completes the booking, and sends a completion notification.

Using the RAMP SDK, the agent-side code for this entire interaction is approximately 30 lines of Python (Listing 1).

Listing 1. Agent-side HITL interaction using the RAMP SDK.

```

from ramp_sdk import RampAgent, ActionOption, RiskAssessment

agent = RampAgent(
    agent_id="agent:flight_search",
    gateway_url="http://localhost:8000",
    api_key="your-api-key",
    principal_id="user:you",
)

async with agent:
    await agent.send_telemetry(
        state="EXECUTING",
        task_description="Searching flights..."
    )
    await agent.send_notification(
        title="Found 3 flights",
        body="Delta, United, American"
    )
    response = await agent.request_action(
        title="Book Delta DL-402?",
        body="$420, non-refundable.",
        options=[
            ActionOption(action_id="book",
                          label="Book Flight"),
            ActionOption(action_id="skip",
                          label="Cancel"),
        ],
        risk=RiskAssessment(
            risk_level="high",
            reversibility="irreversible",
            estimated_cost_usd=420.0),
        timeout_seconds=300,
        fallback_action_id="skip",
    )
    if response.selected_action_id == "book":
        print("Booking confirmed.")
  
```

6 ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION

6.1 Design Tradeoffs

Gateway-mediated vs. direct communication. The gateway-mediated architecture adds a network hop but enables server-side policy enforcement, centralized audit, multi-agent budget aggregation, and principal availability decoupling. The alternative, direct agent-to-human communication, would require embedding governance logic in every agent (trusting untrusted code) and would preclude cross-agent governance (aggregate budget constraints cannot be enforced by individual agents). We argue the centralized enforcement point is architecturally necessary for governance integrity, analogous to how firewalls enforce network policy at a chokepoint rather than trusting each endpoint.

Mandatory timeout vs. blocking HITL. Requiring a timeout and fallback on every Action Request sacrifices human control in edge cases (what if the human needs more time?) in exchange for a system-wide safety guarantee (no agent ever hangs indefinitely). This is a deliberate tradeoff: the alternative (optional timeouts) leads to the failure mode observed in every existing ad-hoc HITL system, where a single unresponsive principal blocks an entire agent pipeline. The timeout value is configurable up to 86,400 seconds (24 hours), providing flexibility within the safety constraint. For decisions requiring longer deliberation, the agent may re-issue the Action Request with a fresh timeout upon expiry, preserving the safety invariant while accommodating extended human decision timelines.

Required risk assessment. Mandating a risk assessment on every Action Request, even for low-risk actions, adds friction to agent development. The rationale is twofold: (1) it forces agent developers

to explicitly reason about risk at design time, and (2) it provides the structured metadata that the governance engine requires for policy evaluation and that audit records require for compliance. The alternative (optional risk assessment) leads to a governance engine that cannot function when the data it needs is absent.

Protocol compliance cost. RAMP’s mechanical requirements (HMAC-SHA256 signing, monotonic sequence numbers, UUID nonces, canonical JSON serialization, and long-poll timeout management) are computationally trivial but must be executed deterministically. This positions them squarely in the host runtime (SDK, tool wrapper, or process supervisor) rather than in the agent’s reasoning loop. For LLM-based agents, the practical prompt-side cost of RAMP integration is a tool description of approximately 100 tokens, comparable to any other external tool binding; the cryptographic and state-management burden is borne entirely by native code. This separation is architectural, not incidental: Principle 2 (*Minimal agent burden*) was designed to ensure that RAMP remains viable regardless of whether the agent is an LLM, a reinforcement-learning policy, or a traditional software agent.

Structural vs. semantic boundaries. RAMP distinguishes between *structural* constraint violations (actions outside the declared capability scope, budget overruns, temporal violations) and *semantic* deviations such as objective drift or task-irrelevant behavior. Structural violations are enforced deterministically by the Gateway’s policy engine via `action_scope`, `resource_constraint`, `time_constraint`, and `rate_constraint` rules, which produce auditable `suspend_and_notify` or `deny_and_notify` enforcement actions. Notably, session wall-clock duration is itself a `resource_constraint`: the principal declares a maximum duration (e.g., 1,800 seconds), and the Gateway enforces it from its own clock, requiring no agent self-reporting. Semantic deviations, by contrast, require intent-level reasoning that is outside the protocol’s scope: RAMP defines message semantics, not agent cognition (Section 3.1). However, RAMP’s telemetry stream, which carries the agent’s declared task description, progress, and resource consumption at regular intervals, provides the structured data surface that a Gateway application layer or external supervisory system needs to detect semantic drift. Upon detection, the existing state-machine primitives (forced suspension via the kill switch, policy-triggered `SUSPENDED` transitions) provide the enforcement mechanism. This separation ensures the protocol remains deterministic and formally verifiable while remaining composable with higher-level supervisory intelligence.

More precisely, RAMP’s enforcement mechanisms fall on a trust spectrum. Temporal constraints (`time_constraint`, `wall_time_seconds`), rate limits, state machine transitions, and cryptographic verification are enforced from the Gateway’s own observations and require no agent cooperation. Cost estimates (`llm_cost_usd`, `estimated_cost_usd`) and risk classifications (`risk_level`, `reversibility`) are agent-declared metadata; the protocol structures and transmits them, but their accuracy depends on the agent’s fidelity or on independent verification via the Corroboration Hook. This architectural separation cleanly delineates what the protocol guarantees autonomously from what requires external corroboration, and it informs deployment decisions: high-stakes environments should pair RAMP governance with

Corroboration Hook integrations that cross-check agent-declared values against authoritative sources.

Linear audit chain vs. concurrent sessions. RAMP enforces a linear hash chain with monotonically increasing sequence numbers per session, which guarantees strict temporal ordering of all auditable events. This design restricts each agent to a single active session; an agent that needs to perform concurrent tasks must multiplex them within one session’s state machine or register multiple agent identities. The alternative (supporting multiple concurrent sessions per agent) would require replacing the linear hash chain with a Merkle directed acyclic graph (DAG), where events from different sessions are linked through a partial ordering and merged at synchronization points. While a Merkle DAG preserves tamper-evidence, it significantly complicates audit verification (from a single linear scan to a graph traversal) and introduces ambiguity in event ordering across sessions. We chose the linear chain for its simplicity, deterministic verifiability, and alignment with the single-agent-single-principal trust model; Merkle DAG extensions are a candidate for the multi-tenant Level 4 conformance tier.

6.2 Security Analysis

RAMP’s threat model assumes an honest-but-imperfect agent: the agent attempts to faithfully report its activities and risk assessments, but may contain bugs or make errors. RAMP does *not* defend against a deliberately malicious agent that fabricates risk assessments to bypass governance (e.g., declaring `estimated_cost_usd`: 0 for a \$1,000 transaction). This scoping is consistent with analogous trust assumptions in infrastructure protocols: HTTP does not defend against a server that lies about its `Content-Length`; OAuth does not defend against a token holder who is also the attacker.

For deployments requiring verified risk corroboration, the protocol defines a *Corroboration Hook*, a synchronous extension point invoked by the Gateway before policy evaluation that may override agent-declared risk values with externally verified data.

Defense-in-depth positioning. RAMP is designed to operate as one layer within a defense-in-depth stack, not as a standalone security perimeter. We identify four complementary layers: *Layer 0 (Infrastructure)*—cloud IAM policies, network firewalls, and service mesh authorization provide hard ceilings on what any process can access, regardless of protocol behavior. *Layer 1 (Tool)*—MCP access-control lists constrain an agent may invoke, limiting its action surface at the tool-binding layer. *Layer 2 (Protocol)*—RAMP governance policies constrain *when* and *under what conditions* the agent may act, based on its self-reported state, risk assessment, and organizational rules. *Layer 3 (Audit)*—the hash-chained audit trail provides post-hoc forensic detection, enabling identification of policy violations, anomalous patterns, or fabricated risk declarations after the fact. A deliberately malicious agent that fabricates risk metadata may bypass Layer 2 governance, but remains constrained by Layer 0 and Layer 1 hard ceilings and is detectable through Layer 3 forensic analysis. This layered framing is consistent with established security architecture principles: no single layer is assumed to be sufficient, and each layer compensates for the failure modes of adjacent layers.

The HMAC-SHA256 + nonce + sequence number scheme provides protection against:

- **Message tampering:** HMAC verification detects any modification.
- **Replay attacks:** Nonce uniqueness within the timestamp window, combined with monotonic sequence numbers, prevents duplicate processing.
- **Impersonation:** Per-agent shared secrets prevent one agent from producing valid signatures for another. The scheme does *not* protect against:
 - **Compromised shared secret:** An attacker with the secret can produce valid messages. Mitigation: key rotation support with 24-hour grace period.
 - **Gateway compromise:** A compromised gateway can tamper with state. Mitigation: agents may independently log messages for reconciliation; the audit chain enables detection.
 - **Side-channel attacks:** Timing analysis of HMAC computation. Outside scope.

6.3 Limitations

We identify the following limitations of the current work:

- (1) **No empirical evaluation at scale.** The reference implementation demonstrates correctness and design validity, not production performance. Load testing, latency benchmarks, and concurrent multi-agent scenarios are needed. A user study evaluating developer experience and cognitive load during RAMP integration is planned as part of future empirical work.
- (2) **Single-gateway architecture.** The specification does not address gateway federation, cross-gateway audit reconciliation, or multi-region deployments. These are deferred to future work.
- (3) **No policy management wire protocol.** The specification defines policy schemas and evaluation semantics, but does not specify HTTP endpoints for creating, updating, deleting, or listing policies. The reference implementation uses configuration-time policy injection. A production system would require a policy management API.
- (4) **No formal verification.** The state machine, policy precedence logic, and hash chain integrity have not been subjected to formal verification (e.g., TLA+, Alloy). We rely on specification-level reasoning and test coverage.
- (5) **Shared-secret cryptography.** The current scheme uses HMAC with pre-shared secrets. Asymmetric cryptography (agent identity certificates, signed messages) would provide stronger non-repudiation guarantees and is a v0.3 consideration.
- (6) **Approximate JCS canonicalization.** The reference implementation uses Python’s `json.dumps` with sorted keys as an approximation of RFC 8785 (JSON Canonicalization Scheme). This covers all data types used by RAMP but does not handle edge cases in number serialization (e.g., exponential notation normalization). Production deployments should use a dedicated JCS library.
- (7) **Adoption dependency.** The protocol’s utility is proportional to adoption by agent frameworks. The specification is architecturally sound, but impact depends on ecosystem integration.

6.4 Regulatory Alignment

We map RAMP’s capabilities to the requirements of the EU AI Act, Article 14 [8]:

- *“Understand the capacities and limitations of the AI system”:* RAMP telemetry provides real-time visibility into agent state, progress, and resource consumption.
- *“Correctly interpret the output”:* Action Requests include structured risk assessments with reversibility, cost, impact scope, and justification.
- *“Be able to decide not to use the system or to override/reverse the output”:* The principal may deny any Action Request, suspend any agent at any time (kill switch), or rely on governance policies that auto-deny prohibited actions.
- *Auditable records:* The hash-chained audit trail records every agent action and human decision.

We emphasize that this mapping is *architectural*, not a formal compliance assessment. RAMP provides protocol-level primitives that support compliance; formal conformance certification requires assessment by qualified bodies against specific deployment contexts.

6.5 Comparison with Existing Approaches

Table 2 compares RAMP’s capabilities with MCP, A2A, and representative ad-hoc approaches. RAMP is the only approach providing structured HITL with mandatory timeout and fallback, declarative governance with formal precedence, cross-agent budget controls, and tamper-evident audit, all as protocol-level primitives rather than product features.

7 FUTURE WORK

Several directions extend the current work:

Human directives. The current protocol is agent-initiated: agents send messages and request decisions. A natural extension is *principal-initiated directives*: messages from the principal to the agent outside the context of an Action Request (e.g., “change your search to include London”). This shifts the interaction model from asymmetric to bidirectional.

Clarification loops. Adding a `request_clarification` resolution type that pauses the timeout clock and asks the agent to provide additional information before the human decides.

Sub-agent hierarchies. The current specification treats agents as independent entities sharing a principal and aggregate budget. Full parent-child agent relationships with policy inheritance and causal tracing across delegation chains are needed for complex orchestration frameworks.

Formal verification. TLA+ or Alloy models of the state machine and policy evaluation logic would provide stronger correctness guarantees. Key properties to verify include: (1) the absorbing-state invariant (no transition out of `TERMINATED`), (2) the governance monotonicity property (a normative deny is never overridden by `auto_resolution`), and (3) the audit completeness property (every state transition produces exactly one audit record).

Table 2. Protocol capability comparison. ✓ = natively supported; ~ = partial or client-side only; – = not supported.

Capability	MCP	A2A	RAMP	Notes
Agent → Human telemetry	–	–	✓	Real-time state, progress, resources
Structured HITL	~	~	✓	MCP: binary client-side; A2A: input-required
Timeout + fallback guarantee	–	–	✓	Mandatory on all Action Requests
Risk assessment metadata	–	–	✓	Required: level, reversibility, cost, scope
Governance policy enforcement	–	–	✓	6 governance rules + auto-resolution, formal precedence
Cross-agent budget controls	–	–	✓	aggregate_constraint
Tamper-evident audit trail	–	–	✓	Hash-chained, 25 event types
Agent lifecycle state machine	–	~	✓	A2A: task-scoped; RAMP: agent-scoped
Multi-principal routing	–	–	✓	Role-based: owner, approver, observer, auditor

Empirical evaluation. Benchmarking gateway throughput, HITL response latency distributions, and governance engine overhead under concurrent multi-agent workloads.

Framework integrations. Adapters for LangChain, CrewAI, AutoGen, and LlamaIndex would demonstrate cross-framework interoperability and lower adoption barriers.

Cryptographic upgrades and evidence. The specification defines a cryptographic agility profile (Section 11.4 of the specification) recommending JWS with Ed25519 as a SHOULD-level upgrade for production deployments. Additionally, the optional evidence field on Action Responses (Section 8.4) enables non-repudiable audit trails by attaching human authentication proofs (WebAuthn assertions, OTP receipts) at the gateway layer, without changing the core signing mechanism.

MCP tool bindings. Canonical MCP tool definitions (ramp_request_approval, ramp_send_telemetry) are documented as an informative integration guide. A reference RAMP MCP Server that translates tool calls into signed RAMP envelopes would make the protocol immediately accessible to any MCP-enabled agent.

Multi-modal principal interfaces. The transport-agnostic design naturally extends to principal interfaces beyond web and mobile: voice-based approval via smart speakers, augmented-reality dashboards for industrial deployments, and ambient notification surfaces. These modalities would require defining interaction-specific timeout and confirmation semantics within the existing Action Request framework.

8 CONCLUSION

As autonomous agents gain the capability to take consequential actions on behalf of humans, the need for a standardized oversight protocol becomes not merely useful but essential. The current landscape of ad-hoc notification mechanisms, framework-specific approval flows, and absent governance is architecturally inadequate for the scale, stakes, and regulatory requirements of production agent deployment.

We have presented RAMP, a protocol that fills the Agent-to-Human layer of the agent protocol stack. RAMP defines five primitives organized around three functions: **Observe** (telemetry, notifications), **Decide** (action requests with mandatory timeout, risk assessment, and structured options), and **Govern** (declarative policy enforcement with formal precedence, tamper-evident audit).

These primitives are implemented through a gateway-mediated architecture with three roles (Human Principal, Agent, Gateway).

The protocol’s core technical contribution is the integration of mandatory temporal safety bounds and declarative governance as first-class communication primitives, rather than a product feature or afterthought. By enforcing spending limits, capability constraints, operating hours, rate limits, and cross-agent budgets at the protocol’s gateway layer, RAMP ensures that governance cannot be bypassed by individual agent implementations.

RAMP complements MCP (Agent-to-Tool) and A2A (Agent-to-Agent), completing the protocol triangle needed for safe, auditable, governance-compliant agent deployment at scale. The specification, reference implementation, and SDK are available as open-source software to support adoption, extension, and independent verification.

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